

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DRUG-INDUCED BLACK HAIRY TONGUE IN A POST-GASTRECTOMY PATIENT

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ABSTRACT

A 67-year-old female patient with a history of Billroth I gastrectomy (2010), chronic atrophic gastritis, and recurrent peptic ulcer disease developed black hairy tongue following *Helicobacter pylori* eradication therapy containing antibiotics and bismuth. Examination revealed a dense black-brown coating on the posterior two-thirds of the tongue, halitosis, vitamin B12 deficiency, riboflavin deficiency, hypoacidity, and *Candida albicans* overgrowth. The condition was considered drug-induced, likely exacerbated by long-standing hypoacidic atrophic gastritis and impaired B-vitamin metabolism. Comprehensive treatment, including rabeprazole, probiotics, pancreatic enzymes, B12 and riboflavin supplementation, antifungal therapy, and tongue hygiene, led to near-complete resolution within three weeks and healing of gastric ulcers. In this patient with prior gastric surgery, black hairy tongue was most likely induced by recent antibiotic therapy and oral candidiasis in the setting of persistent hypoacidity and B-vitamin deficiencies.

Keywords: black hairy tongue, chronic atrophic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, status post-gastrectomy, vitamin B12 deficiency, riboflavin deficiency.

Introduction. Black hairy tongue (lingua villosa nigra) is a benign, fully reversible condition characterized by hyperplasia and hyperkeratosis of the filiform papillae of the tongue, with elongation up to 1–2 cm and black or dark brown discoloration [1,2]. The pigmentation is caused by chromogenic (pigment-producing) bacteria and yeasts that accumulate on the elongated papillae [1,3]. It is not an independent disease but often a symptom or consequence of other conditions, including gastrointestinal (GI) disorders [4,5]. It is not cancer, not an infection (although candidiasis sometimes accompanies it), and is not transmitted to others [1,2]. The main causes include smoking, frequent consumption of strong tea, coffee, red wine, alcohol, antibiotics (especially tetracyclines and penicillins), and poor oral hygiene [1,2,6]. Black hairy tongue has been associated with a range of GI disorders, including both functional and chronic inflammatory conditions [4,5,7]. The condition occurs in 0.6%–11.3% of the population, more commonly in men over 40 years of age and smokers [1,8].

The mechanisms are not fully understood, but the following factors have been suggested:

- Disruption of oral and gut microbiota (dysbiosis) – antibiotics or GI diseases alter bacterial balance, promoting the proliferation of chromogenic microorganisms on the tongue [5,9].

- Decreased stomach acidity (achlorhydria or hypochlorhydric gastritis) – reduces barrier function and facilitates bacterial colonization of the upper GI tract and oral cavity [5].

- Impaired vitamin metabolism – in gastrointestinal diseases, deficiencies of B vitamins often occur, leading to hyperplasia of the papillae [5].

- Reflux and dry mouth – Conditions such as GERD, Zenker's diverticulum, or chronic gastritis are associated with xerostomia and mucosal irritation, creating a favorable environment for the condition [4,10].

- Chronic inflammatory diseases – Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis, and chronic colitis may contribute through systemic inflammation and dysbiosis [5,9].

Aim. To report a case of black hairy tongue associated with peptic ulcer disease, antibiotic therapy, oral candidiasis, and vitamin B deficiency in a 67-year-old woman.

Case Presentation. A 67-year-old woman presented to a gastroenterologist on 20 October 2025 with a history of intermittent heartburn, belching, epigastric heaviness, postprandial weakness, halitosis, and bitter taste in the mouth.

Medical History. Peptic ulcer disease was diagnosed in 2010 and surgically treated for a callous gastric ulcer with Billroth-I gastroduodenostomy. In April 2024, the patient completed a course of *H. pylori* eradication therapy for an exacerbation of peptic ulcer disease with good clinical response. She occasionally took omeprazole on her own during episodes of gastric dyspepsia.

The current worsening began in October 2025 and lasted approximately 1–1.5 months. She sought medical attention for symptoms of gastric dyspepsia, and esophagogastroduodenoscopy performed on 4 October 2025 revealed acute gastric ulcers, Forrest III. Status post Billroth-I surgery (2010). Chronic focal atrophic gastritis. Portal hypertensive gastropathy, grade I by McCormack classification. As prescribed by a physician in a private medical center, she underwent eradication therapy. During the treatment, she first noticed a change in the color of her tongue, which became “brown-black and hairy,” while her taste sensation remained unchanged. She subsequently sought medical care at her local clinic.

Past Medical History. The patient has a history of chronic atrophic gastritis for more than 10 years.

Physical Examination. The tongue was mildly xerotic and covered on its middle and posterior thirds with a dense, black-brown, hair-like coating approximately 1.0–1.5 mm in thickness. The coating was tightly adherent and could not be scraped off with a spatula. The anterior third, tip, and lateral margins of the tongue were pink and spared. The remaining oral mucosa appeared slightly pale. Halitosis was noted. The abdomen was soft and non-distended, with mild tenderness on palpation in the epigastric and pyloroduodenal regions; no rebound tenderness or guarding was elicited.

Laboratory and Instrumental Findings. Complete Blood Count:

- Hemoglobin: 100 g/L (reference: 120-140 g/L)
- RBC: $4.0 \times 10^{12}/L$ (reference: $3.5-5.0 \times 10^{12}/L$)
- WBC: $10.0 \times 10^9/L$ (reference: $4.0-9.0 \times 10^9/L$)

Serum Chemistry:

- Vitamin B12: 127 pg/mL (reference: 200-900 pg/mL)
- Riboflavin (Vitamin B2): 2.8 µg/L (reference: 4-

24 µg/L)

Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD), performed per the hematologist's request, revealed atrophic antral gastritis and acute gastric ulcers. The patient is also status post-Billroth I gastrectomy (2010), and current testing showed the patient to be negative for *H. pylori* (status post-eradication therapy).

pH-metry demonstrated pronounced hypoacidity.

Tongue Swab revealed abundant growth of *Candida albicans* and chromogenic bacteria.

Hematology Consultation. The patient was diagnosed with vitamin B12-deficiency anemia secondary to chronic atrophic gastritis, of mild severity, and riboflavin deficiency-related glossitis.

Dental Consultation. The diagnosis was Glossitis (black hairy tongue), desquamative type, associated with a postoperative hypoacidic gastric state, impaired trophic changes, and disturbances in vitamin B metabolism.

Diagnosis. Primary diagnosis: Drug-induced black hairy tongue (bismuth and antibiotics) following eradication therapy for peptic ulcer disease.

Chronic atrophic *H. pylori*-negative gastritis of mild severity with marked secretory insufficiency. Complications/Comorbidities: Vitamin B12-deficiency anemia secondary to chronic atrophic gastritis, mild severity, and riboflavin deficiency.

Treatment. The patient was managed with the following regimen for 4 weeks:

- Rabeprazole 20 mg once daily for 2 weeks (prescribed short-term for acute ulcer treatment despite the underlying hypoacidity).
- Pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy (Creon®, 25,000 units) with main meals.
- Probiotics (Bifiform®) 1 capsule twice daily for 1 month.
- Vitamin therapy: riboflavin 25 mg orally three times daily for 4 weeks; cyanocobalamin 1000 µg intramuscularly daily for 7–10 days, then 1000 µg weekly for 4–8 weeks, followed by 1000 µg monthly lifelong.
- Local therapy: mechanical cleaning of the tongue with a scraper twice daily, rinsing with a 1% soda (sodium bicarbonate) solution, fluconazole 150 mg orally once, and topical nystatin applied to the tongue four times daily for 10 days.

Recommendations. increased intake of fresh vegetables and fruits; avoidance of strong tea and coffee.

a

Figure 1. Tongue appearance before treatment (a) and after treatment (b)

Outcome. After 10 days of treatment, the tongue showed significant lightening, with the dorsal coating becoming shorter and softer. Halitosis and dysgeusia had resolved by day 14. After 3 weeks, the tongue was nearly completely cleared, with only slight light-brown discoloration remaining on the posterior third. Control esophagogastroduodenoscopy confirmed complete healing of the gastric ulcers.

Conclusion. The presented case illustrates a classic example of drug-induced black hairy tongue triggered by bismuth- and antibiotic-containing *H. pylori* eradication therapy in a patient with multiple synergistic predisposing factors: pronounced gastric hypoacidity due to chronic atrophic gastritis and prior Billroth-I gastroduodenostomy, riboflavin and vitamin B12 deficiency, oral candidiasis, and xerostomia. The tongue showed improvement within 10 days and near-complete resolution by 3 weeks through a comprehensive approach that simultaneously addressed local factors (mechanical debridement with a scraper, alkaline rinses with 1% sodium bicarbonate, topical nystatin and a single dose of oral fluconazole) and systemic predisposing conditions (riboflavin and cyanocobalamin supplementation, pancreatic enzyme replacement with Creon, probiotics, and short-term acid suppression optimization).

This case highlights the importance of patient education, recognition of medication-induced oral manifestations, and interdisciplinary management to address both local and systemic contributing factors.

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